

THE HISTORY OF THE TURKIC PEOPLES AND THE EMBODIMENT OF THE UNITY IN TURKIC STATES

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Abstract. *The science of Turkic studies is to examine the similarities between the Turkic languages and at the same time all the features that distinguish them from each other. From this point of view, it is important to involve the language, ethnic composition, culture, political and economic relations of the Turkic peoples in the study. The influence comes from the fact that the Turkic world is geographically located in the central part of the Eurasian continent, and has always played the role of a connecting bridge between the two great Eastern and Western cultures. In general, it should be noted that mutual relations between Turkic-speaking countries have been developing quite successfully in the last thirty years. Turkic-speaking countries are trying to actively participate in both economic and other fields of activity all over the world. In our modern era, there are great political power games and a struggle for geopolitical supremacy in the world. Against the background of this difficult period in which the world is experiencing political confusion, the importance of Turkish unity stands out more prominently.*

Keywords: turkish, people, culture, language, state, unity, development.

Annotatsiya. *Turkshunoslik fani turkiy tillar o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va shu bilan birga ularni bir-biridan ajratib turuvchi barcha xususiyatlarni tekshirishdan iborat. Shu nuqtai nazardan, turkiy xalqlarning tili, etnik tarkibi, madaniyati, siyosiy va iqtisodiy munosabatlarini o'rganishga jalb etish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Turk dunyosi geografik jihatdan Yevroosiyo qit'asining markaziy qismida joylashganligi va har doim ikki buyuk Sharq va G'arb madaniyatini bog'lovchi ko'priklarni o'ynaganligidan ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Umuman olganda, turkiy tilli davlatlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro munosabatlar keyingi o'ttiz yilda ancha muvaffaqiyatli rivojlanib borayotganini ta'kidlash joiz. Turkiy tilli davlatlar butun dunyoda ham iqtisodiy, ham boshqa faoliyat sohalarida faol ishtirok etishga harakat qilmoqda. Bizning zamonamizda buyuk siyosiy kuch o'yinlari va dunyoda geosiyosiy ustunlik uchun kurash davom etmoqda. Dunyo siyosiy chalkashliklarni boshdan kechirayotgan ushbu qiyin davr fonida turk birligining ahamiyati yanada yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: turk, xalq, madaniyat, til, davlat, birlik, taraqqiyot.

Аннотация. *Наука тюркологии заключается в изучении сходства между тюркскими языками и одновременно всех особенностей, отличающих их друг от друга. С этой точки зрения важно вовлечь в исследование язык, этнический состав, культуру, политические и экономические отношения тюркских народов. Влияние исходит из того, что тюркский мир географически расположен в центральной части Евразийского континента и всегда играл роль связующего моста между двумя великими восточной и западной культурами. В целом следует отметить, что взаимоотношения между тюркоязычными странами в последние тридцать лет развиваются достаточно успешно. Тюркоязычные страны стараются активно участвовать как в экономической, так и в других сферах деятельности во всем мире. В нашу современную эпоху происходят великие политические игры и борьба за геополитическое превосходство в мире. На фоне этого сложного периода, когда мир переживает политическую дисбаланс важность турецкого единства выделяется еще более заметно.*

Ключевые слова: турки, народ, культура, язык, государство, единство, развитие.

For a long time, the Turkic world has been a unique place where powerful cultures and civilizations were born and developed, and had a great influence on the course and formation of world history. The science of Turkic studies is to examine the similarities between the Turkic languages and at the same time all the features that distinguish them from each other. From this point of view, it is important to involve the language, ethnic composition, culture, political and economic relations of the Turkic peoples in the study. The influence comes from the fact that the Turkic world is geographically located in the central part of the Eurasian continent, and has always played the role of a connecting bridge between the two great Eastern and Western cultures. It is generally accepted that Central Asia, considered the homeland of the Turks' ancestors, played an important role in the spread of Turkic tribes and peoples throughout the world. It is recorded in one of the books: "As a result of the migrations of the steppe communities of Central Asian origin, one of the areas in which they have been active since the early times was the wide geography called "Eastern Europe" in general terms. The Turkish presence in the region started with the Scythians in the centuries before Christ and continues until today. It would not be wrong to say that it has reached".[1.p,25]

The development of Turkic peoples has many common features. Everything from geographical location, language, culture and historical characteristics to the similarity of reforms carried out in the modern stage of development united the peoples of the species. Today, the Turkic world continues to develop and prosper. These countries cooperate with each other in various fields such as economy, politics, culture, science. The Turkic world is known for the variety of Turkic languages. However, there is a fact of similarity that linguists consider indicative of the existence of a single common source language from which all modern languages evolved in complex and diverse ways in the past. One of the most famous Turkish linguists and scholars is Mahmud Kashgari. He was born in Kashgar (modern China) in the 11th century and wrote *Divan lugat at-turk*, one of the first books on Turkish language and culture. This three-volume classic work on Turkish lexicography appeared in 1074-1075. The originality and originality of the work is confirmed by the author's words: "Such a dictionary has never been compiled by anyone, and it was compiled in a special order that no one knows." Mahmud Kashgari wrote several great scientific works, most of which have unfortunately been lost without a trace. Fortunately, the main work of his life - the 700-page monumental work "*Divan Lüğat et-Turk*" - has been preserved. The only and oldest copy of the manuscript is kept in the National Library of Turkey. According to researchers, the book has become a real encyclopedia of Turkish folk life in the early Middle Ages. In addition to the language of the Turks, there is also information about the geography, customs, and religious views of the Turks. The dictionary gives a broad idea of the tribal composition of the Turks, the lands, lakes and rivers, cities and settlements of the Karakhanid state. As Mahmud Kashgari aims to review only the words related to the Turkish language, the dictionary includes clothing, household items, agricultural products, weapons, musical instruments, family and tribal relations, titles, utensils, animal and plant names, day, month, city, disease, there are words that define medicines. Also, 29 Turkish tribes are named in the *divan*. The author claimed that at that time there were 20 Turkic languages and dialects, which in turn were divided into smaller languages. Mahmud Kashgari is a very talented person for his time. He created a unique, incomparable dictionary, which became one of the most valuable monuments of the culture and history of the Turkic peoples. Modern oriental studies, including Turkic studies, cannot be

imagined without his work. Mahmud Kashgari's book is important not only as a philological and historical source, but also as a collection of socio-philosophical thoughts of the Turkic peoples and as a promotion of ethical behavior norms. Mahmud Kashgari is the eldest son and honor of all Turkic peoples, an outstanding scientist who made invaluable contributions to the history and culture of these peoples. Thus, the existence of the Turkic peoples, their ancient culture, language, and history is conveyed to the whole world thanks to such works. The ancient roots of the Turkish people, the strong Turkish unity and culture that unites them challenge the whole world even in our present time. Today, the Turkic states, their strong political and economic development make the entire Turkic world happy.

In general, it should be noted that mutual relations between Turkic-speaking countries have been developing quite successfully in the last thirty years. It is said in the sources: "Today, a more suitable environment than ever has been created for us to get to know the Turkish World more closely in all its fields and fronts. Scientists who are interested in the homeland of the Turkish nation are no longer viewed from the side of a political cadre, or through Turanist or fascist eyes. In any case, these were baseless views in the past." [4.p,29] Turkic-speaking countries are trying to actively participate in both economic and other fields of activity all over the world. Continuous integration processes of the Turkic peoples also bring up the issue of the feasibility of creating a single program to ensure economic security. The Organization of Turkic States is a policy aimed at protecting the rights of our compatriots living not only in the member states, but also in the world. In addition to political, economic, trade, cultural, transport, energy, digital transformation, agriculture, tourism has become more active in areas such as security, defense, energy industry.

The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, especially noted that the Turkic world is not only composed of independent Turkic states, but its geographical boundaries are wider. He said that the time has come to pay attention to issues such as the protection of the rights, security, and national identity of our compatriots living outside the countries that are members of the Organization of Turkic States, and their assimilation on a permanent basis within the framework of the organization. Currently, as one of the most spectacular examples of Turkey's policy of supporting Turks, we can point to the active participation of Turkish companies as contractors in many infrastructure projects in the large-scale construction works carried out in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan.

The fact that a school will be built by Uzbekistan and a creative center by Kazakhstan in the liberated Fuzuli region is an indication of the brotherhood between Azerbaijani-Uzbek and Azerbaijani-Kazakh peoples. At the same time, Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan's repeated visits to our liberated lands and his presence in Karabakh is a high manifestation of support for the people of Azerbaijan. One of the sources very correctly states that: "The Shusha Declaration signed between Azerbaijan and Turkey was a cornerstone in the strengthening of military, political and economic relations within the framework of the OTS. This declaration symbolizes the deepening alliance between these two nations and serves as a model for cooperation between other Turkish states. plays". [2.]

Today, there are great political power games and a struggle for geopolitical supremacy going on in the world. It has been recorded very well: "It is necessary to look at the Turkish world in the 21st century by taking into account the change and transformation that politics and the state are undergoing. In other words, it is easy to understand and make sense of the Turkish world with the codes of the last century". [3.] Against the background of this difficult period in which the world is experiencing political confusion, the importance of Turkish unity stands out more

prominently. We saw the visual demonstration and importance of this again during the 44-day Patriotic War. We witnessed that responding to the global political crises and all the forces against our national interests with the strong unity of the Turks gives our states additional strength. It always makes us winners.

We believe that the Turkish people and Turkish culture will always be able to assert themselves in the whole world and will be at the forefront in all fields thanks to the mutual support of the Turkish states and the Turkish brotherhood.

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